

Monthly Briefing #5 - January 2025

A new year, fresh energy and a strong circular drive ahead!

As we enter 2026, United Circles continues to develop the ideas and collaborations that keep our circular value chains moving forward. This monthly report is intended for reflection, as always 😊, to keep us inspired as the journey continues. In January, what are we focusing on?

European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform: a joint initiative of the European Commission and the European Economic and Social Committee

For those of you who are familiar with it, we present the European Platform of Stakeholders in the Circular Economy. It is a joint initiative of the European Commission and the European Economic and Social Committee. This initiative brings together businesses, public authorities, NGOs, and citizens to share knowledge, good practices, and strategies that support the transition to a circular economy. It fosters collaboration, policy dialogue and learning to accelerate circular solutions across sectors and regions in Europe.

More information here:

[European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform](#)

Clean Industrial Deal: a plan for EU competitiveness and decarbonisation

Although the Clean Industrial Agreement was launched almost a year ago (26 February 2025), we would like to reflect on the importance of circularity within it. The Circular Economy Act, expected to be adopted later this year, will ensure that scarce materials are used and reused efficiently (the goal is to achieve 24% of materials circular by 2030).

All information here:

[Clean Industrial Deal](#)

United Circles Stakeholder Community

Join the United Circles Stakeholders Community and connect with organisations, experts and innovators driving circular change across Europe. Share insights, exchange good practices, and help shape sustainable solutions for water, materials and regional development. By engaging with this network, you become part of a collaborative ecosystem committed to turning circular economy ideas into real impact.

Be part of the transition!

[Get involved today](#)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101178798. This work is supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).